

Design and freezing performance study of a CO₂ plate freezer at -50°C evaporation temperature

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ABSTRACT

Efficient cooling and freezing systems using natural refrigerants offer a sustainable solution for food loss and waste reduction in the food supply chain, particularly by preventing the loss of raw materials. Plate freezers are typical components in modern automated production and processing facilities for freezing processed foodstuffs. At NTNU, a real-sized industrial plate freezer has been implemented into a dedicated CO₂ refrigeration system in the laboratory infrastructure. Due to CO₂ liquid circulation inside the plates, the unit can provide more than 100 kW of cooling capacity at evaporation temperatures between -30 and -50°C. This study aimed to design the test facility for the proposed plate freezer and numerically investigate the freezing performance. Component sizing was performed using established principles and techniques to accommodate the refrigerant properties. The freezing time evolution for different product masses was analyzed. Furthermore, the effects of evaporation temperature on the freezing time were investigated.

Keywords: Refrigeration, Carbon Dioxide, Plate Freezing, Freezing Time, Energy Efficiency

1 INTRODUCTION

Food loss and waste are responsible for at least 6% of total global greenhouse gas emissions. Nearly two-thirds of the emissions come from losses across the supply chain, resulting from poor storage and handling techniques, and a lack of refrigeration or spoilage in transport and processing. Efficient cooling and freezing systems using natural refrigerants are a sustainable solution for food loss and waste reduction in the food supply chain, especially for the prevention of the loss of raw materials. Global fish and seafood consumption will continue to increase and is expected to reach 21.4 kg per capita by the end of this decade (OECD, Food et al. 2021). Therefore, there is a large demand for the freezing of processed fish and other foodstuffs. Plate freezers are typical components in modern automated production and processing facilities, which consist of vertical or horizontal stack hollow plates. Plate freezers are flexible in operation as batch processing, semi-continuous or continuous processing. In addition, they are categorized as quick freezers and can freeze large quantities of meat or fish.

Plate freezers using NH₃ as the refrigerant are difficult to reach evaporation temperatures lower than -35°C and have application constraints due to the toxicity and flammability of NH₃. However, plate freezers using CO₂ as the refrigerant can achieve a fast temperature decrease with an evaporation temperature as low as -50°C (Dopazo and Fernández-Seara 2012, Verpe, Bantle et al. 2018). In addition, CO₂ is environmentally friendly, non-toxic, and non-explosive, which makes it an ideal refrigerant in food processing. Moreover, due to the high heat transfer rate and less defrosting frequency of the heat transfer surface, the operation cost of CO₂ plate freezers is low, and the maintained product quality is high with little dehydration. Therefore, the CO₂ plate freezer technology has a huge commercial potential to satisfy both food manufacturers and customers.

This study aimed to design a test facility for a real-sized industrial plate freezer which can be

implemented into a dedicated CO₂ refrigeration system in the laboratory infrastructure. The unit can provide more than 100 kW of cooling capacity at evaporation temperatures between -30 and -50°C. In addition, a numerical model was established for the proposed freezing system and the freezing performance was numerically investigated for different evaporation temperatures and product masses.

2 DESIGN OF THE PLATE FREEZING TEST FACILITY

In this study, a plate freezing system was designed to be implemented into an existing CO₂ refrigeration system in the laboratory infrastructure which can be applied to fish freezing on onboard fishing vessels and fish and meat processing. Due to CO₂ circulation, the unit can provide more than 100 kW of cooling capacity at evaporation temperatures between -50°C and -30°C. The test facility will be used to investigate and optimize the performance of the freezing system and its components.

2.1 CO₂ plate freezing system description

The existing CO₂ heat pump system has three suction lines with different suction temperatures and one supply line. A horizontal plate freezer is incorporated into the CO₂ system working as a flooded evaporator. The working principle of the plate freezing system is shown in Figure 1. The CO₂ liquid at the outlet of the condenser is at 14°C and 50 bar. Through the expansion valve, the high-pressure liquid CO₂ is throttled to -50°C and 6.8 bar. Then the two-phase CO₂ is separated in a separator to ensure that only liquid CO₂ is pumped into the plate freezer. In the freezer, the liquid CO₂ is evaporated by absorbing the cooling duty from the product to be frozen. The liquid-vapor mixture from the plate freezer is then directed back to the separator and the CO₂ vapor goes back to the suction line of the central CO₂ system. When the experiment is completed, the refrigerant in the plate freezing system will be directed back to the receivers of the central CO₂ system to prevent the high standstill pressure.

Figure 1: Working principle of the proposed CO₂ plate freezing system

A CO₂ plate freezer test facility was designed based on the above-mentioned concept and the system P&ID is shown in Figure 2. The test facility will be applied to investigate and optimize the plate freezing technology for fast food freezing between horizontal plates. The freezing time, evaporation temperature, product center temperature, energy consumption, and production capacity will be monitored during the experiment and further analyzed to minimize emission footprints, energy consumption, and investment costs. In addition, the test facility will also include a defrosting circuit using hot gases to defrost the plates at the end of the freezing process.

Figure 2: P&ID of the plate freezing test facility

2.2 Components design

As shown in Figure 2, the main components of the plate freezing test facility consist of a subcooler, a separator, a pump, a plate freezer, a compressor, and an expansion valve (V3). The compressor is used for the defrosting circuit.

2.2.1 Subcooler

The CO₂ liquid from the supply line of the central CO₂ refrigeration system is at 14°C and 50 bar. A subcooler is installed to ensure that only liquid CO₂ to be throttled by the expansion valve (V3) before the separation tank. Through the subcooler, CO₂ liquid is expected to be cooled from 14°C to -33°C.

The cold stream is obtained by throttling the subcooled CO₂ by an automatic expansion valve (V2) to -38°C and 10.8 bar, as shown in Figure 3. The subcooling process is under constant pressure and the cooling load is:

$$\dot{Q}_{subcooler} = UA * LMTD \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

The logarithmic mean temperature difference LMTD is calculated as:

$$LMTD = \frac{(T_{hot,in} - T_{cold,out}) - (T_{hot,out} - T_{cold,in})}{\ln \left(\frac{T_{hot,in} - T_{cold,out}}{T_{hot,out} - T_{cold,in}} \right)} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

The calculated LMTD is around 20 K and the required subcooling capacity for cooling CO₂ from 14°C to -33°C at 50 bar is 18 kW, corresponding to the UA value of around 1000 W/K. The installed subcooler in the lab is shown in Figure 4.

The expansion valve (V2) operates according to the setpoints of the temperature sensor (T1) and pressure sensor (P1) to control the superheat at the outlet (P4) and make sure only vapor CO₂ goes back to the -38°C suction line of the central CO₂ system.

Figure 3: Streams through the subcooler

2.2.2 Expansion valve (V3)

Through the expansion valve (V3), the liquid CO₂ is throttled from -33°C and 50 bar to -50°C and 6.8 bar. The electronic expansion valve (V3) was sized according to the maximum capacity of the lowest-stage compressors in the central CO₂ system. Three compressors operate in series at the lowest compression stage with a suction temperature of -48°C and suction volumes of 18.4 m³/h, 28.9 m³/h, and 28.9 m³/h, respectively. The maximum suction volumetric capacity V_{max} is a summation of the suction volumes of the three compressors:

$$\dot{V}_{max} = \dot{V}_1 + \dot{V}_2 + \dot{V}_3 \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

The volumetric efficiency (η) of the compressors is chosen to be 0.6, a conservative value according to Bitzer Software. Then the maximum mass flow rate (kg/s) can be calculated as:

$$\dot{m}_R = \frac{\dot{V}_{max} * \eta * \rho}{3600} \quad \text{Eq. (4)}$$

The maximum cooling capacity is:

$$\dot{Q}_{cooling} = \dot{m}_R * (h_{out} - h_{in}) \quad \text{Eq. (5)}$$

where ρ is the vapor density (kg/m³), h_{out} and h_{in} are the enthalpies (kJ/kg) at the outlet and inlet of the plate freezer.

The expansion valve (V3) was sized based on the maximum mass flow rate of 0.23 kg/s and cooling capacity of 80 kW with an opening of 80%. The model selection was conducted by Coolselector software and Danfoss CMT08 model was chosen, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: The separator and subcooler in the lab

2.2.3 Separator

The liquid and vapor two-phase separation is realized in the separator in three stages. The first stage is the primary separation and is achieved by diverters at the separator inlets, as shown in Figure 5. Larger droplets impinge on the diverter due to the momentum and then fall due to gravity. The secondary separation occurs in the disengagement area between the diverters and demisters as the smaller droplets detach from the vapor flow and fall due to gravity. The third stage is the demisting. The smallest droplets are coalesced into larger droplets in the demisters and fall under gravity.

As shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5, a horizontal separator with three demisters in series was chosen. The sizing of the separator was determined according to the method presented by Svrcek and Monnery (1993). The holdup and surge time of the tank are 5 min and 2 min, respectively. The calculated diameter of the separator tank which can ensure adequate falling time for liquid droplets is 500 mm and the separator length is 1000 mm.

A perforated plate is placed over the liquid outlet of the separator to avoid the incomplete separation of the mixture due to a short circuit from the inlet directly to the outlet. The plate has an inclination angle of 3° to facilitate the liquid flow throughout the tank and obtain an adequate separation time. The separator tank inclines 2.5° opposite to the inclination of the perforated plate to assist the liquid flowing out of the tank. After the separation, the liquid phase leaves the separator from the outlet at the bottom and goes to the pump, while the vapor phase leaves the tank from the top vapor outlet and is sent back to the -48°C suction line of the central CO_2 system.

As shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5, sight glasses were installed in the middle of the separator shell and

at the liquid outlet so that the CO₂ liquid level could be monitored. The liquid column level was set above 2.4 m. The control range of the liquid level is from 0 to 400 mm above the set value of the liquid column, which can be covered by the effective observing length of the sight glasses at the liquid outlet of the separator. The CO₂ liquid level is controlled by the expansion valve (V3) according to the pressure difference between the separator top pressure and the pressure at the pump inlet, which is measured by a differential pressure sensor. Because the liquid CO₂ is at a constant temperature of -50°C and with a constant density of 1155 kg/m³, the pressure difference is proportional to the liquid column height ($\Delta P \propto \Delta h$) according to $P = \rho gh$. When the reading of the DP sensor is smaller than the set value, the opening of V3 will be increased to send more CO₂ into the separator. Instead, if the reading of the DP sensor is larger than the set value, the opening of V3 will be decreased. If the liquid level reaches the middle height of the tank, the liquid level switch will be activated and the V3 will be closed to prevent the further increase of the liquid level.

Figure 5: Schematic diagram of the separator tank

2.2.4 Plate freezer

The liquid CO₂ at around -50°C and 6.8 bar from the separator is pumped into the plate freezer which can provide a cooling load of 40 kW. Inside a plate, CO₂ as the refrigerant flows through the coils and is evaporated by absorbing heat from the product. The CO₂ plate freezer was manufactured by Optimar AS. The relevant technical data of the plate freezer is illustrated in Table 1. The plate freezer in the lab is shown in Figure 6. After the evaporation, the liquid-vapor mixture is directed back to the separator.

Table 1. Technical data of the plate freezer

Plate number	4
Orientation	Horizontal
Dimensions including the frame	3150 x 2150 x 2580 mm
Plate dimensions	2480 x 1605 x 27 mm
Design pressure	50 bar
Filling volume	12 l per plate

Figure 6: CO₂ plate freezer in the lab

The mass flow to the plate freezer is measured by a mass flow meter (M2) and controlled by a control valve (V4) with a mass flow control unit, as shown in Figure 2. If the reading of the M2 is higher than the set value, the opening of the V4 will be increased and more refrigerant will be returned to the separator, and vice versa.

2.2.5 Defrosting compressor

After the freezing process is completed, the defrosting of the plate freezer will be activated. An auxiliary compressor is employed to supply hot gas to the freezer by utilizing the gas CO₂ from the -8°C suction line of the central CO₂ system. The freezer works as a condenser and the compressed hot gas is condensed by releasing heat to the plates and frozen food. The condensate is then sent back to the 14°C supply line of the central CO₂ system.

The capacity of the defrosting compressor was sized to be able to defrost the frozen products wrapped with a 1 mm ice layer in a short period (approximately 10 min). The required defrosting load is the summation of the sensible heat required to raise the plate and ice temperature from -50°C to 0°C and the latent heat needed to melt the ice layer. The calculated compressor capacity was 3 kW with a discharge temperature of 30.9°C according to the mass and energy balance. A Dorin CD360H compressor was selected for the defrosting circuit. A variable speed driver (VSD) is used to control the compressor speed or frequency according to the defrosting demand.

2.3 Instrumentation and data acquisition

The instrumentation of the test facility is shown in Figure 2. The inlet mass flow rate of the separator and the liquid mass flow rate to the plate freezer are measured by mass flow meters M1 and M2, respectively. Each plate was equipped with 10 thermocouples so that the temperature distribution on the plate surface can be captured. In addition, each product block (fish fillets) was installed with 10 thermocouples to measure the center temperature. Plate B (the second plate from the bottom) is the test plate. The pressure drop across the Plate B is measured by a differential pressure sensor (DP-02). Each plate was also equipped with a PT-100 temperature sensor at the refrigerant outlet to monitor the superheat. The control strategies of the test facility have been explained in the component design

in Section 2.2. The data acquisition and processing of the analog measurement signals of all the equipped measuring instruments are achieved by National Instrument components with the LabVIEW software.

3 NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF THE PLATE FREEZING SYSTEM

A dynamic numerical model of the CO₂ plate freezing system was developed by Dymola (Dynamic Modelling Library, version 2022, Dassault systems) (Systèmes 2022) using Modelica language. Two commercial Modelica libraries were utilized for the simulations, namely TIL-suite 3.10.0 and TILMedia 3.10.0 which are provided by TLK-Thermo GmbH. The system model and component models were all established based on the designed plate freezing system introduced in Section 2.

3.1 Numerical model

A simplified simulation model of the freezing process is illustrated in Figure 7. To simplify the simulation, the pressure drops caused by friction in the system and heat losses to the surroundings were neglected.

Figure 7: Simplified model of the freezing process

A plate heat exchanger model was employed to simulate the heat transfer in the subcooler. To simplify the simulation, the pressure drop across the subcooler was neglected. The evaporation heat transfer coefficient was calculated by the Longo correlation (Longo, Mancin et al. 2015) and the single-phase heat transfer was calculated by Martin correlation (Martin 1996).

The plate freezer was simulated by a tube exchanger with a capacitor heat boundary to model the heat flow from the product with an initial temperature of 18°C and different masses of the product. The evaporation heat transfer coefficient was calculated by the Gungor and Winterton (1987) correlation and the single-phase heat transfer was calculated by the Gnielinski (1975) correlation and Dittus and Boelter (1985) correlation. The pressure drop was calculated by Konakov (1946) correlation.

Because the ice in the fish products forms over a range of temperatures rather than at a single temperature, a temperature-dependent effective heat capacity, which considers both the sensible and latent heat effects, was used in the simulation according to Schwartzberg (1976). Cod muscle was chosen as the frozen product by assuming homogenous material and regular shape and the parameters in Schwartzberg (1976) were used for the effective heat capacity calculation.

The liquid and vapor phases were assumed at thermodynamic equilibrium in the separator. The volume of the separator was 0.2 m³ and the initial filling level was set at 40%. The pump was running at a constant mass flow rate with an efficiency of 0.4. The expansion process was assumed to be isenthalpic and at the outlet of the expansion valve, the liquid-vapor two-phase flow is at a thermodynamic equilibrium state. The expansion valves V2 and V3 are controlled by PI controllers

according to the superheat at stream point ④ and the freezer evaporation pressure, respectively.

3.2 Simulation results

The evolution of the product core temperature with different product masses is illustrated in Figure 8. The refrigerant mass flow rate through the plate freezer was maintained at 0.5 kg/s in the simulation. The freezing time to freeze 173 kg cod muscle from 18°C to -30°C is 81 min and the freezing time increases proportionally to the product mass.

The freezing process can be divided into three periods. The first period is the cooling down of the product to the freezing temperature. It takes around 17 min when the product mass is 173 kg. The second period is the freezing of the water content and it takes approximately 47 min. In this period, the product temperature remains constant due to the large fusion latent heat of the water content. The third period is the further cooling down of the frozen product to -30°C and it takes about 17 min. The freezing rate is higher in this period because of the lower specific heat capacity of the frozen product compared to the fresh product.

The evolution of the product core temperature with different evaporation temperatures is illustrated in Figure 9. To freeze 173 kg cod muscle from 18°C to -20°C, the required freezing times are 76 min, 96 min, and 133 min for the evaporation temperatures of -50°C, -40°C, and -30°C, respectively. The increase in the evaporation temperature significantly increases the freezing time in the second period as well as the minimum reachable temperature. Decreasing the evaporation temperature from 30°C to 50°C, the freezing time can be reduced by 43%, which is consistent with the results from Verpe, Bantle et al. (2018).

Figure 8: Evolution of the product core temperature with different product masses

As shown in Figure 10, the vapor quality at the outlet of the plate freezer decreases during the freezing process following the same trend as the product temperature. In the first period, the high temperature difference between the product and the plates ensures a high evaporation rate. In the second period, the vapor quality stays at a relatively constant value as the product temperature remains constant. In the third period, due to the lower specific heat capacity of the frozen product, the temperature difference between the product and the plates drops quickly and the vapor quality also quickly falls. The vapor mass flow rate at the outlet of the separator also follows the same trend, as shown in Figure 10.

The circulation rate is defined as the ratio between the circulated refrigerant mass flow rate to the vapor mass flow out of the freezer. Because the plate freezer works in batches, the thermal load is not constant but declines during the freezing process. Therefore, with a constant feed liquid mass flow rate, the circulation rate of the plate freezer increases throughout the whole freezing process, as shown in Figure 10. At the end of the freezing process, the circulation rate is very high due to the low vapor quality at the outlet of the freezer.

Figure 9:

Figure 10: The Evolutions of the vapor quality at the outlet of the plate freezer, circulation ratio, and vapor mass flow out of the separator

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a plate freezing system which can be applied to fish freezing on on-board fishing vessels and fish and meat processing was designed. A real size industrial horizontal plate freezer was implemented into an existing CO₂ heat pump system in the laboratory infrastructure working as an evaporator. Due to CO₂ circulation, the unit can provide more than 100 kW of cooling capacity at

evaporation temperatures between -50°C and -30°C. The designed test facility will be employed to test and analyze the freezing time, evolution of the CO₂ evaporation temperature, center temperature of the frozen product, energy consumption, and production capacity of the designed plate freezing system.

Furthermore, a numerical simulation was conducted for the designed plate freezing system and the freezing times with different product masses and different evaporation temperatures were analyzed. The results showed that the freezing time to freeze 173 kg cod muscle from 18°C to -30°C is 81 min and the freezing time increases proportionally to the product mass. In addition, by decreasing the evaporation temperature from 30°C to 50°C, the freezing time can be reduced by 43%. Moreover, with a constant feed liquid mass flow rate, the circulation rate of the plate freezer increases throughout the whole freezing process.

A thorough experimental study will be conducted after the completion of the construction of the test facility. The performance of the freezing system as well as the components will be investigated and optimized with this test facility. The numerical model will also be validated and improved by the experimental results. Additionally, a new model including the central CO₂ system will be developed to simulate the overall performance and efficiency of the plate freezing and CO₂ refrigeration system.

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